

Gender Diversity Effecting Teachers Classroom Management Practices at Higher Education Level

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Abstract

The major objectives of the study were to explore the prevailing classroom management practices at higher level among teachers and to compare teacher's classroom management practices on the basis of gender. The research in hand was based on quantitative approach. Further by method the research was based on comparative style of research. The population of the study was based on 8659 social sciences students (Male=4795, Female=3864 sessions) enrolled in public sector universities of Islamabad (Session 2022). Stratified random sampling technique was used to select the sample. 447 social sciences students contributed in data collection process among which 251 were male and 196 were female. The data was collected with the help of self-developed questionnaire based on the model of classroom management practices presented by Fraser, McRobie and Fisher (1996). The questionnaire was based on 44 items and six sub scales (Teacher's cohesiveness, Teacher's support, Teacher's involvement, Teacher's investigation, Task orientation, Teacher's cooperation and Teacher's equity). The scale was found reliable at .906 while the sub-scales were found reliable .703, .746, .815, .618, .680, .850 and .660 respectively. Respondents agreed that the teachers were practicing classroom management skills related to cohesiveness, teachers, support, involvement, task orientation, cooperation and equity. However, among these above seven areas there respondent strongly agreed with the teacher's practices regarding equity. That was showing that teachers answer the questions of the students, students were allowed to ask questions freely and discuss the content, use of appreciation and cooperation on the part of the teacher. Further there was statistically no significant ($t = .240$) difference between male and female respondents regarding the use of the classroom management practices. The same was the situation with the sub scales. It was recommended that the teachers need to manage a discussion session with the class on the first day to decide about the expectation from the class and classroom rules. To appreciate the good efforts made by the students the teacher need to celebrate the success of the students with in the class with the class fellows. To develop cohesiveness among the students the teachers need to assign group projects and social work assignments such social work would also help them to become a productive citizen of the country.

Keywords: Classroom Management, cohesiveness, support, involvement, investigation, Task Orientation, cooperation and equity

1. Introduction

Classroom is a central figure in the formal Education system all over the world. This is the place of learning for the student. No one can deny the importance of classroom in the educational experience of the students. A classroom is not only a building having certain type of furniture and required material, but it is much more than a collection of material. It is an environment in which a student spends 5-6 hours daily. During this time the child not only uses the furniture and other material but also interacts with peers and teachers. Provision of comfortable environment within the classroom can increase child's attention spoke and learning ability. A classroom is made of 4 basic resources, material resources, human resources, informational resources and financial resources.

Material resources include Furniture, Boards, Instructional aids etc. However, these resources are static unless someone use it for a specific purpose. Human resources includes teachers, students and supporting staff etc. Among all of these teacher is the most important and central figure. Teacher is the person who regulates the material resources and develop a learning environment. Informational resources include books, content, internet web sites, you tube clip etc. While financial resources work on the background of everything. Finance is the major factor that make material, human and informational resources available.

Thus in this way a classroom is developed. To utilize a classroom in effective way, there is a need to manage the resources in an efficient manner. This management depends on the ability of Teacher. The same classroom becomes a different one with the change of only a person known as "Teacher".

Classroom management is an art. This art can be learning with the time and experience. This is one of the most important side of the school. This management is a skill that can be developed among teachers through trainings. At all levels of education, it is equally important.

However, the researcher selected the higher level of education to explore the status of classroom management practices by the teachers. As universities are considered the major pillars in the education system and have better facilities as

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compared to schools and colleges. This the research interested to explore the demographic variation among teachers effecting the classroom management practices.

1.1. Research Objectives

- To explore the prevailing classroom management practices at higher level among teachers.
- To compare teacher's classroom management practices on the basis of gender.
 - 2a To compare teacher's cohesiveness on the basis of gender.
 - 2b To compare Teacher's support on the basis of gender.
 - 2c To compare teacher's Involvement on the basis of gender.
 - 2d To compare teacher's Investigation on the basis of gender.
 - 2e To compare teacher's Task orientation on the basis of gender.
 - 2f To compare teacher's cooperation on the basis of gender.
 - 2g To compare teacher's equity on the basis of gender.

1.2. Null Hypothesis

Ho1: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's classroom management practices on the basis of Gender.

Hola: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's cohesiveness on the basis of Gender.

Holb: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's support on the basis of Gender.

Holc: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's involvement on the basis of Gender.

Hold: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's investigation on the basis of Gender.

Hole: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's task orientation on the basis of Gender.

Holf: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's cooperation on the basis of Gender.

Holg: There is statistically no significant difference in Teacher's equity on the basis of Gender.

1.3. Significance of the Study

The study in hand would be significant in multiple ways. It will directly address the teacher's. Students and management of higher education institutions. Further the parents and society will also get benefit in the larger context. The Teachers would be beneficiaries of the research in a way that the researcher will suggest the maximum ways to improve the classroom situations / environment. The suggestions of the study would help the teacher to manage their classrooms in a unique and creative manner.

The students will get benefits in a way that they would avail the better learning environment. The suggestions of the study will focus on the learning of the students. The research would propose the way to manage classroom as an interactive learning place for students.

The management would get suggestive measures to be used to make their institution a better learning organization. The management can utilize the suggestions of this research to provide training sessions to the teachers.

2. Literature Review

"Management" refers to the arrangements of resources in order to get the maximum benefit from the minimum resources. Management is the heart of every field of life (Froyen and Iverson, 1999). Human life depends on managing and arranging the things to make the environment around us comfortable for living (Crone and Horner, 2003). Some is the case with the environment of the classroom. Arranging the resources available in a school for the facilitation of teaching and learning is called as classroom management (Emmar and Anderson, 2004). Classroom is not only a collection of some chairs and a v aids but it is much more than this. Classroom environment is a combination of two different factors one is physical factors and the second is the psychological factors (Evertson and Emmer, 1982). In this way the classroom environment is a very rich source of facilities that ensure the teaching learning process to happen. To arrange all these factor in a proper manner is called as classroom management (Marzano, 2003). Researches have proven that teachers with more experience can manage the classroom better than the less experienced teachers. In this way classroom management can be taken as a teaching skill. Skill is an art of doing something well (Yaduma and Abdulhanud, 2007)

To learn any skill one needs time and practice (Bear, Cavalier and Manning, 2005). Some is the case with classroom management skill. It need to be the part of teacher training programs but to learn it as a teaching behavior one need time to invest and practice on containers basis (Kanchale and Eggen, 2008). Barnes (1999) reported that classroom management depends upon the quality of teacher training programs. It need to be a central point in all teacher training courses. Further (Iaccio (2004) reported that as a result of classroom management the student's academic achievement is increased. It directly effects on the student's learning. Classroom discipline effects on the quality of instruction positively (Haltie, 2012). Class management also has a positive effect on time management of the teachers (Buger, Mohr and Walls, 2002) classroom management plan helps the teachers to save time during the class and help to increase the student attention span (Alderman, 2004).

Both physical and psychological factor of classroom are equally important to produce and effective learning environment. Physical areas are the physical facilities such as furniture, a voids, books, content, space etc. it maintains the concrete side of the classroom. While of the same time there is an abstract side of the classroom as well (Levin and Nolan, 2007). This abstract side is the psychological side of the class. It consisted of the factors that are not directly observable such as I.Q. level, interests, motivation, multiple intelligence etc. These factors are hard to control (Gurney,2007). Classroom management overs the both as to maintain a conducive learning environment.

3. Methodology

The research in hand was based on quantitative approach. Further by method the research was based on comparative style of research. Gender was decided as the base for the comparison of Teacher's classroom management practices. The population of the study was based on 8659 social sciences students (Male=4795, Female=3864 sessions) enrolled in public sector universities of Islamabad (Session 2022). Stratified random sampling technique was used to select the sample. 447 social sciences students contributed in data collection process among which 251 were male and 196 were female.

The data was collected with the help of self-developed questionnaire based on the model of classroom management practices presented by Fraser, McRobie and Fisher (1996)

The questionnaire was based on 44 items and of scales (Teacher's cohesiveness, Teacher's support, Teacher's involvement, Teacher's investigation, Teacher's cooperation and Teacher's equity).

The data was collected with the personal visits of the research to the public sector universities of Islamabad. The data was analyzed by using Mean and independent sample t test mainly.

Table 1: Reliability of classroom management practices scale (n=447)

Scale	Sub scales	items	Reliability
Classroom management practices scale		44	.906
	Cohesiveness	CO1-CO7 (7)	.703
	Teacher support	TS1-TS6 (6)	.746
	Involvement	IV1-IV6 (6)	.815
	Investigation	IN1-IN6 (6)	.618
	Task orientation	TO1-TO5 (5)	.680
	Cooperation	CP1-CP8 (8)	.850
	Equity	EQ1-EQ6 (6)	.660

The table 1 shows the reliability of the scale used in the research. It explains that classroom management practices scale was reliable at .906. While its sub scale related to cohesiveness, Teacher's support, involvement, investigation, task orientation, cooperation and equity were found reliable .703, .746, .815, .618, .680, .850 and .660 respectively.

Table 2: Item total correlation of classroom management practices assessment scale (n=447)

item	r	Item	r	item	R	item	r
CO1	.403**	TS5	.370**	IN4	.231**	CP4	.717**
CO2	.335**	TS6	.581**	IN5	.420**	CP5	.544**
CO3	.558**	IV1	.581**	IN6	.263**	CP6	.361**
CO4	.370**	IV2	.333**	TO1	.385**	CP7	.401**
CO5	.668**	IV3	.316**	TO2	.577**	CP8	.423**
CO6	.591**	IV4	.391**	TO3	.432**	EQ1	.534**
CO7	.600**	IV5	.357**	TO4	.259**	EQ2	.506**
TS1	.691**	IV6	.475**	TO5	.521**	EQ3	.594**
TS2	.691**	IN1	.466**	CP1	.688**	EQ4	.399**
TS3	.322**	IN2	.377**	CP2	.549**	EQ5	.420**
TS4	.600**	IN3	.242**	CP3	.632**	EQ6	.447**

Table 2 explains the item total correlation of the items included in the classroom management practices assessment scale. All the items included in the scale were found statistically significantly correlated with each other at 0.01 level of significant. The way of this correlation was between 0.231** to 0.717**.

Table 3: Inter section correlation of classroom management practices assessment scale (n=447)

	Cohesiveness	Support	Involvement	Investigation	Task	Cooperation	Equity	Management
Cohesiveness	1							
Support	.659**	1						
Involve	.355**	.230**	1					
Investigation	.249**	.533**	.405**	1				
Task	.387**	.665**	.161**	.143**	1			
Cooperation	.689**	.554**	.184**	.143**	.457**	1		
Equity	.402**	.672**	.537**	.580**	.546**	.417**	1	
Management	.804**	.844**	.541**	.558**	.643**	.773**	.782**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 explains the interaction correlation between the sub scales of the classroom management practices scale. The highest correlation was found between Teacher's support and classroom management (.844**) while the lowest correlation was found between sections related to investigation and task orientation (.143**).

Table 4: Prevailing classroom management practices (n=477)

Variable	Sub Variable	N	Mean	Status
Management		447	4.28	Agreed
	Cohesiveness	447	4.02	Agreed
	Support	447	4.27	Agreed
	Involve	447	4.23	Agreed
	Investigation	447	4.35	Agreed
	Task	447	4.19	Agreed
	Cooperation	447	4.28	Agreed
	Equity	447	4.64	Strongly Agreed

Table 4 explains the teacher's classroom management practices. The response of the respondents was showing that they agreed with the statements regarding classroom management practices. They agreed that the teachers were practicing classroom management skills related to cohesiveness, teachers, support, involvement, task orientation, cooperation and equity. However among these above seven areas there respondent strongly agreed with the teacher's practices regarding equity. That was showing that teachers answer the questions of the students, students were allowed to ask questions freely and discuss the content, use of appreciation and cooperation on the part of the teacher.

Table 5: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management practices (n=477)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Classroom Management	Male	251	188.34	.240	445	.811
	female	196	188.58			

Table 5 shows that there was statistically no significant ($t = .240$) difference between male and female respondents regarding the perception about the use of classroom management practices. Thus the hypothesis No 1 is accepted.

Table 6: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management related to Cohesiveness (n=477)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Cohesiveness	Male	251	28.00	1.57	445	.116
	female	196	28.40			

Table 6 explains that there was statistically no significant ($t=1.57$) difference found in the response of male and female respondents regarding the sub variable related to cohesiveness. Thus the hypothesis 1a is accepted.

Table 7: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management related to Teacher Support (n=477)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Teacher support	Male	251	25.66	.126	445	.900
	female	196	26.64			

Table 7 explains that male and female respondents were having same perception about the teacher's support provided to the students ($t=0.126$) thus hypothesis 1b is accepted.

Table 8: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management related to Involvement (n=477)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Involvement	Male	251	25.31	1.10	445	.268
	female	196	25.49			

Table 8 explains that statistically again no significant ($t=1.10$) difference found between male and female respondents related to the use of classroom involvement skills by the teachers. Thus, hypothesis 1c is accepted.

Table 9: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management related to Investigation (n=477)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Investigation	Male	251	26.13	.188	445	.851
	female	196	26.10			

Table 9 describes that there was statistically no significant difference ($t=.188$) found related to investigation between male and female respondents. Thus the hypothesis 1d is also accepted.

Table 10: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management related to task orientation (n=477)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Task orientation	Male	251	20.90	.670	445	.503
	Female	196	21.01			

Table 10 describes again that there was statistically no significant ($t=.670$) difference found between male and female respondents with reference to task orientation in this way hypothesis No 1e is accepted as well.

Table 11: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management related to

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Cooperation	Male	251	34.38	.710	445	.478
	female	196	34.15			

Table 11 represents that male and female respondents were equal ($t=.710$) in their opinion related to teacher's cooperation during the classroom. Thus hypothesis No 1f is accepted.

Table 12: Gender based comparison of teachers classroom management related to

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Equity	Male	251	27.96	1.08	445	.281
	female	196	27.78			

Table 12 describes that there was statistically no significant ($t=1.08$) difference found between male and female respondents related to their opinion about equity as practiced by the teachers. Thus, hypothesis 1g is accepted.

4. Discussion

The research in hand was gender based comparative analysis of teacher's classroom management practices. The researchers developed null hypothesis to avoid gender biasness in the result management is an art that can be learnt with practice.

Still certain researches have proved that the female teachers are better in organizing the classroom discipline. Female teachers are proffered to teach at pre-school and primary level more as compared to male teachers (Yaduma and Abdulhamid, 2007). The following research was focused on 7 areas of classroom management that were cohesiveness,

teacher's support, involvement, investigation, task orientation, cooperation and equity. The researcher involved students to inquire about the classroom management practices used by their teachers. The higher level of education was focused because of 2 major reasons. One the higher education Institutions have its importance being the institutions producing the highly educated graduates so teachers at this stage are supposed to be the well trained personnel in managing and handling the classroom and students. Second the students at higher level of education are well aware and can answer in better way to the questions in which the researcher was interested. The findings of the study showed that there was no statistically significant difference was found between male and female students with reference to any area of classroom management. In this way all the hypothesis of the study was accepted. The study was conducted in the federal area of Pakistan and the conditions here are much better than the other cities if Pakistan. However, if the same study may be conducted in other cities of Pakistan, may be there would be different findings. As certain

Studies shows that there is statistically significant difference between male and female students with reference to teaching styles (Marzano,2003). Classroom management is almost different at deferent levels of education (Kavhak and Eggen, 2008). Male and female teachers have different preferences in selecting the professions. Females prefer the teaching as profession more as compared to male teachers. It is also observed that students at primary level feel more comfortable with female teachers. Unfortunately, at higher level in Pakistan of Education there is no pre-service teacher education is required on compulsory basis. They are only offered in service teacher training. Thus at this level male and female both need to be trained in the art of teaching and teaching skills (Evertson and Emmer, 1982).

4.1. Recommendations

- a. As majorly no statistically significant difference was found between male and female respondents related perception related to teacher's classroom management practice. Thus following are the suggestion that are propose for male and female both to improve their classroom management skills
- b. Teachers need to develop his / her own personality traits as he / she want to see in the students. This role model idea would help the students to understand better what the desired behavior from then is.
- c. The teachers need to manage a discussion session with the class on the first day to decide about the expectation from the class and classroom rules.
- d. To appreciate the good efforts done by the students the teacher need to celebrate the success of the students with in the class with the class fellows.
- e. Teachers need to appreciate the students who take initiatives. Such as who volunteer to be the first presenters teachers support.
- f. To develop cohesiveness among the students the teachers need to assign group projects and social work assignments such social work would also help them to become a productive citizen of the country.
- g. To ensure the student involvement teachers need to arrange discussion sessions once in a month. This session would help the students to share their unique and innovative ideas with peers.
- h. To develop the habit of investigating the teachers need to encourage the innovative idea from the students.
- i. To focus on task orientation, the teachers need to provide some short activities on individual basis. These short activities may be of one page so that everyone can complete it easily and will not create academic burden as well.
- j. To focus on equity, the teachers need to ask questions during the class. Everyone in the class need to be encouraged to answer. In this way everyone will be involved in the session and students will learn to think in a different way.

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